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Gardening systems and the use of pesticides and fertilisers: an ever-changing dynamic: the view of gardeners in the lowland of Nedialepoun, Burkina Faso

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ABSTRACT

This study analyses the dynamics of market garden cropping systems and the impact of pesticide and fertiliser use. The methodology combines secondary and primary data. Descriptive statistics, the relative importance index, the impact frequency index and ordered logistic regression were used to process the data. The study showed that market gardeners have several market gardens cropping systems, including eight cropping systems before the development of the lowland and thirteen cropping systems today. The dynamics of the cropping systems are accompanied by a high frequency of pesticide and fertiliser use. The study also shows that the dynamics of pesticide and fertiliser use are influenced by the type of market targeted by the growers, the type of vegetables grown, the level of the water table, climatic variables, the level of education, the size of the plots and the level of equipment used by the growers.

Keywords: pesticides, dynamics, market gardening system, determinants, lowland

1. INTRODUCTION

Once used for picking and livestock rearing, lowland areas have become indispensable with the advent of climate variability in West Africa. In Burkina Faso, the lowlands are used for market gardening in rural areas. This structures the socio-economic life of the rural population (Yanogo et al., 2019). However, pests and diseases are major constraints to vegetable production, as are agronomic constraints, water unavailability and flooding (Kapeleka et al., 2021, Kapeleka et al., 2024). As a result, vegetable yields in market garden plots remain relatively low, even under irrigated conditions, despite their yield potential under appropriate management conditions. The use of pesticides has become a necessity for market gardeners in Burkina Faso.

This is made possible by low market prices. These products make it possible to limit the damage caused by crop pests and diseases (Yaméogo, 2021). Because of the harmful effects of these pests on yields, the number of pesticides used is increasing every year (Sawadogo, 2016). However, several studies show that pesticides have harmful effects on the human and physical environment.

Pesticides could reduce certain microbial populations while leaving others unaffected, thereby reducing competition for resources shared by affected and unaffected populations, leading to soil degradation (Staley, 2015; Karpouzas, 2021; Majumder et al., 2021). In human terms, the short-term effects of exposure to pesticides include headaches, skin irritations, vision problems, respiratory problems, dizziness and nausea (Ntow et al., 2006). In Burkina Faso, the situation is alarming in lowland market gardening. Several toads, frogs and insects have disappeared from market garden plots, and health problems have arisen due to the use of pesticides (Son et al., 2017; Sanou et al., 2020, Yaméogo, 2021).

Although previous studies have revealed the effects of pesticide exposure on the environment and health, pesticide use remains high among a number of market gardeners who continue to use them intensively in the lowland plots of Nediapoun, in the Sanguié region of Burkina Faso. This raises the question of what factors influence market gardeners' decisions to use pesticides. The main objective of the study is to analyse the dynamics of market gardening and the determinants of the intensive use of pesticides and fertilisers by market gardeners in the Nediapoun lowland.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study area

The study area is located in the centre-west region of Burkina Faso. The Nediapoun lowland is located in the commune of Réo, which is the capital of the Sanguié province (Fig.1).

2. 2. Sampling procedures and Data collection

The method of data collection is based on secondary and primary data. The secondary data was obtained from various virtual libraries and on the net. The primary data was obtained through surveys carried out during the period November-December 2024. they were carried out using survey forms. Purposive sampling was used on the basis of two criteria: the use of pesticides in the sites and the use of fertilisers in the sites. The sample size is calculated according to the Marien and Baud formula (2003) as follows:

$$n = \frac{1}{e^2} \tag{1}$$

where: n = sample size, e = margin of error = 5%, $n = 1 / (0.05)^2 = 400$

The total population is estimated at 150 people, whose number varies according to the season (dry and/or wet). In 2021, the number of farmers was 200 (Yaméogo et al., 2021). This makes it difficult to estimate the number of market gardeners, which is dynamic from year to year and season to season. Nevertheless, estimating the number of gardeners is a good thing because it shows the dynamism of gardeners. Moreover, if the total population is less than 400 persons, Marien and Baud 2003 suggest a correction factor defined as follows:

$$n' = \frac{N \times n}{N + n} \tag{2}$$

where: n' = corrected sample; N = total population size; n = sample size; $n' = 400 \times 150 / 400 + 150 = 109.09$. As a result, 109 peoples were surveyed.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the Nedialpoun lowland.

2. 3. Method of data analysis

2. 3. 1. Relative Importance Index (RII)

This index is used to assess the importance of the causes of error in construction (Kometa et al., 1994, Sambasivan & Soon, 2007, Abd El-Razek et al., 2008; Gündüz et al., 2013, Rashid et al., 2018). This index was used by Yanogo, 2024 to determine the importance of market gardening systems in a context of climate variability in Burkina Faso. However, the author used the degree of importance. In this study, the relative importance index was chosen to capture the dynamics of the importance of market gardening systems in market gardening sites.

The relative importance index is calculated according to the following formula (Jarkas & Bitar, 2012, Aziz et al., 2016):

$$RII(\%) = \frac{3(n_3)+2(n_2)+n_1}{3(n_1+n_2+n_3)} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where: $n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4,$ and n_5 = the number of respondents who selected:

1 = somewhat important

2 = important

3 = very important.

In the relative importance index (RII), values approaching 100 could indicate more important elements (Doloi, 2009, Jarkas & Bitar, 2012).

2. 3. 2. Impact Frequency Index (IFI)

The impact frequency index was based on the frequency index used by Bekr, 2015 to classify the causes of delay according to the frequency of respondents. According to Bekr, 2015, Yaméogo & Sawadogo, its formula is:

$$IFI = \frac{\sum X \times (\frac{n}{N}) \times 100}{4} \quad (4)$$

where: X is the constant expressing weight given to each response (range from 1 to 4), n is the frequency of the response and N is the total number of responses.

The IFI was used to understand market gardeners' perceptions of the frequency of pesticide and fertiliser use in lowland areas. The field surveys identified several types of fertilisers (urea, NPK and compost). 90% of respondents use urea and NPK (nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium), and 10% compost. Pesticides, particularly insecticides, are used on market garden plots (Table 1).

When a crop requires both pesticides and fertilisers, the frequency of impact is high. However, it is rare for a crop to require both pesticides and fertilisers. According to 80% of those surveyed, the requirements of market garden crops differ from one crop to another. Table 2 below summarises.

Table 1. The main pesticides used on market garden plots.

Commercial name	Type of pesticide Active	Active substance and concentration	Frequency of citation	WHO toxicity category
Acarius 018 EC	Acaride	Abamectine 18 g/l	30%	II
CAIMAN B19	Cotton insecticide	Emamectine benzoate	10%	II
K-OPTIMAL	Insecticide	Lambda-cyhalothrine 15 g/l	50%	
LAMBDA SUPER 2.5C	Insecticide	Lambda-cyhalothrine 25 g/l	10%	III

Source: Field investigations, 2024, Yaméogo, 2021.

Table 2. Frequency of demand for pesticides and fertilisers for vegetables.

Vegetables	Pesticides (insecticides)	Fertiliser (urea, NPK + compost)
Onion	-	+
African eggplant	+	-
Cucumber	-	+
Tomato	+	-+
Chilli	+	-
Cabbage	+	-+
Carrot	-+	-+
Mint	-+	-+
Celery	-+	-+
Eggplant	+	-+
Okra	-+	-+

Source: Field investigations, 2024, + = increase, - = decrease, -+ = medium

In the lowlands, growers are opting for a combination of vegetable crops. This changes the extent to which pesticides and fertilisers are used.

2. 3. 3. Ordinal Logistic Regression Model

Several studies in Thailand (Kangkhetkron & Juntarawijit, 2021), Ghana (Tham-Agyekum et al., 2023) and India (Kathiravan & Georges, 2023) have used logistic regression as a method to analyse the determinants of pesticide use. In this study, ordinal logistic regression was used to analyse the determinants of the increase in pesticide and fertiliser use in the Nedialpoun lowlands.

The advantage of the ordered probit model is that it allows the dependent variable to take values other than 0 and 1 (Hasan, 2017). The variables related to the determinants of pesticide use are ordered categorical variables. The ordered logistic model is an estimation technique in which there is an observed ordinal variable, Y (Alotaibi et al. (2021). There is also an unmeasured latent variable y^* with different thresholds. The general form of the ordered logistic model is as follows (Jeder et al., 2018):

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_i X_i + e \tag{5}$$

where: Y = level of perceived use of pesticides and fertilisers (low use, medium use, high use, very high use)

β_0 = Constant

β_i = Parameters to estimate

X_i = Variables observed (socio-economic factors, type of vegetable, type of market, climatic variables, level of equipment)

e = Term of error

For the ordinal variables observed in the study, three (03) response categories were used: 1 = never use of pesticides and fertilisers, 2 = rarely use of pesticides and fertilisers, 3 = sometime use of pesticides and fertilisers and 4 = usually use of pesticides and fertilisers. The categorical variable Y has different thresholds. Furthermore, the value of the observed variable Y depends on whether a threshold is crossed or not. In this study, the probability that an individual belongs to one of the four categories depends on the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_i = 0 \text{ (Never use of pesticides and fertilisers), if } Y^* \text{ is } \leq K_1 \\ Y_i = 1 \text{ (Rarely use of pesticides and fertilizers), if } Y^* \text{ est } \leq K_2 \\ Y_i = 2 \text{ (Sometime use of pesticides and fertilizers), if } Y^* \text{ est } \leq K_3 \\ Y_i = 3 \text{ (Usually use of pesticides and fertilizers), if } Y^* \text{ est } \leq K_3 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

2. 3. 3. 1. The variables selected for the ordinal logistic regression model

Ordinal logistic regression is used to explain a qualitative ordinal variable (the dependent variable) and an independent variable which is both quantitative and qualitative.

- **The study's dependent variable**

It is constructed on a Likert scale as follows: never, rarely, often and usually. The aim is to understand the determinants of pesticide and fertiliser use in the Nediaipoun lowland.

- **The independent variables**

They concern socio-economic variables, climatic variables, the level of the water table, the type of market and vegetables (Table 3).

Table 3. Details of the explanatory variables selected.

Variables	Type	Description
Age	Categorical	1 = [21-30]
		2 = [10-20]
		3 = [31-40]
		4 = [41-50]
		5 = [51-60]
		6 = [61-70]
Gender	Dichtomous	1 = Male
		2 = woman
Level of education	Dichtomous	1 = instructed 2 = non instructed
Household size	Categorical	1 = 1-3 2 = 3-4 3 = 5-9
Income level	Categorical	1 = ≥ 300000 FCFA/year, 2 = ≥ 1 million/year, 3 = ≥ 2 millions/year
Equipment level	Dichtomous	1 = high 2 = low
Climatic variable	Dichtomous	1 = extreme temperature 2 = extreme rainfall
Plot size	Categorical	1 = 0.25 ha 2 = 0.5 3 = +1 ha
Type of market	Dichtomous	1 = City-oriented market 2 = local market
Type of vegetables used	Dichtomous	1 = local consumption vegetable 2 = urban consumption vegetable

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of market gardeners

The characteristics of market gardeners in the lowlands are diverse. Men dominate, as do the educated in lowland market gardening in the study site (Figure 2).

Figure 2(A,B). Dominance of men and educated people among market gardeners

There is a diversity of age groups, with young people and adults predominating. However, 90% of respondents have between 1 and 5 people in the household, with 77.3% having an annual income of $\geq 300,000$ FCFA (Table 4).

Table 4. Socio-demographic characteristics of market gardeners.

Age group	Frequency	Percentages
[21-30]	30	27.3
[10-20]	13	11.8
[31-40]	30	27.3
[41-50]	23	20.9
[51-60]	9	8.2
[61-70]	4	3.6
Total	109	100
Number of people in the household	Frequency	Percentages
1-3	57	51.8

3-4	44	40
5-9	8	7.3
Total	109	100
Level of income	Frequency	Percentages
≥ 300,000 FCFA	85	77.3
≥1 million FCFA	18	16.4
≥ 2 millions FCFA	6	5.5
Total	109	100

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

3. 2. Changes in market-gardening systems and factors influencing the use of pesticides and fertilisers in the Nediapoun lowlands

According to the respondents (80%), the lowland was developed several years ago. Two periods can be identified in this development, which also coincides with the dynamics of lowland cropping systems in the study site. These were the period before and after the lowland was developed.

- **Period without development of the lowland**

At the beginning of the 2000-2010 period, the Nediapoun lowlands were still undeveloped. This situation limits vegetable cultivation to 3-4 months, as the water table is depleted during the dry season due to the exploitation of groundwater resources and the lack of rainwater to recharge the water table. During this period, vegetables such as onions, tomatoes, African eggplant, cucumbers, cabbage and okra are the main vegetables used for market gardening (Table 5).

Table 5. Main vegetables grown in market gardening plots before development of the lowland.

Vegetables	Very Important	Important	Somewhat Important	Total	RII%	Rank
Onion	153	64	26	243	74.31%	1
Tomatoe	117	80	20	217	66.36%	2
Cabblage	90	78	40	208	63.61%	3
African eggplant	90	60	40	190	58.10%	4
Cucumber	57	20	60	137	42%	6
Gumbo	87	20	50	157	48%	5

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

The table shows that tomatoes, onions and cabbages play an important role in market gardening. This situation has influenced the market gardening systems in the lowlands (Table 6).

Table 6. The main market-gardening systems promoted before the development of the lowland.

Vegetables	Very important	Important	Somewhat important	Total	RII%	Rank
Onion + tomato	225	64	2	291	90%	1
Tomatoe + cabblage	210	34	22	266	81.34%	3
Cabblage + tomato + onion	270	34	2	306	93.57%	2
African eggplant + onion + tomato	201	40	22	263	80.43%	4
cucumber+cabblage	117	62	39	218	67%	6
Gumbo + African eggplant	60	40	69	169	52%	7
Gumbo + tomato + African eggplant	60	50	59	169	51.70%	8
Chilli + tomato + cabblage	147	42	39	228	70%	5

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

The frequency of use of pesticides (insecticides, herbicides, fungicides) and fertilisers (NPK, urea) varies according to cropping system (Table 7).

Table 7. High frequency of pesticide and fertiliser use.

Vegetables	Low impact	Medium impact	Strong impact	Very strong impact	Total	IFI%	Rank
Onion + tomato	28	56	72	116	272	62%	6
Tomatoe + cabblage	20	40	60	196	316	72.5%	3
Cabblage + tomato + onion	20	20	60	236	336	77%	2
African eggplant + onion + tomato	10	36	69	232	347	79.47%	1
Cucumber + cabblage	23	116	30	72	241	55.3%	8

Gumbo + African eggplant	23	100	54	72	249	57%	7
Gumbo + tomato + African eggplant	18	36	120	132	306	70%	5
Chilli + tomato + cabbage	5	10	30	316	361	72.4%	4
Gumbo + cucumber + onion	30	118	30	40	218	50%	9

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

This table shows that market gardeners make extensive use of cropping systems: African eggplant + onion + tomato, cabbages + tomato + onion, tomato + cabbages, African eggplant + onion + tomato. Pesticide use is high, with impact frequency indices $\geq 70\%$. This could be explained by the fact that the vegetables that make up the cropping systems require both pesticides and fertilisers to achieve good yields. The combination of pesticides and fertilisers means that the impact frequency is high in the period 2000-2010, but what about the period after the development of the lowlands?

- **Period of development of the lowland**

The period 2014-2024 corresponds to the development of the plain with the installation of the micro-dam in the plain. The presence of the micro dam will allow the water table to be recharged. This will lead to an extension of the market gardening period. As a result, the market gardening period has increased from 4 to 6 months per year. The period 2000-2010 was characterised by the predominance of traditional wells, with cropping systems dominated by vegetables such as onions, tomatoes, chillies, cabbage, African aubergines and cucumbers. However, with the development of the lowlands, modern wells have been installed alongside traditional wells, the number of which has increased over this period due to the increased availability of water. The plots are used to grow a variety of horticultural crops, including chillies, cabbages, carrots, celery, mint, tomatoes, aubergines, African aubergines and cucumbers. The importance of these crops varies from plot to plot in the lowlands (Table 8).

Table 8. Main vegetables used after lowland development.

Vegetables	Very important	Important	Somewhat important	Total	RII%	Rank
Onion	216	50	12	278	85%	3
Celery	0	10	104	114	34.86%	10
Eggplant	207	40	20	267	81.65%	5
Tomato	231	44	10	285	87.15%	2
Cabbage	237	40	10	287	87.77%	1

Carrot	9	14	99	122	37.31%	8
African eggplant	162	62	24	248	76%	6
Cucumber	9	14	99	122	37.35%	7
Gumbo	30	44	77	151	46.20%	7
Chill	180	78	10	268	82%	4
Mint	9	4	104	117	35.78%	9

Source: Field investigations, november - december, 2024

This table shows that onions, tomatoes, chillies, cabbage and eggplants are now more widely used by market gardeners with RII% \geq 80%. This reflects their importance in the period 2014-2024. The different crops of importance are alternated by market gardeners, resulting in a diversity of cropping systems during this period (Table 9).

Table 9. Main market-gardening systems after lowland development.

Vegetables	Very important	Important	Somewhat important	Total	RII%	Rank
Onion + tomato	240	52	3	295	90.21%	6
Tomatoe + cabblage	258	42	2	302	92.35%	5
Cabblage + tomato + onion	306	12	1	319	97.55%	2
African eggplant + onion + tomato	306	12	0	318	97.25%	3
Cucumber + cabblage	27	130	35	192	58.71%	7
Gumbo + African eggplant	27	100	50	177	54.13%	9
Gumbo + tomato + African eggplant	15	130	39	184	56.27%	8
Chilli + tomato + cabblage	315	2	3	320	97.86%	1
Gumbo + cucumber + onion	3	30	90	123	37.61%	11
Onion + mint + carrot	3	10	100	113	34.55%	12
Aeggplant + celery	0	2	108	110	33.64%	13
Onion + mint + cabblage	18	26	90	134	41%	10
Chill + onion + cabblage	270	30	4	304	92.96%	4

Source: Field investigations, november - december, 2024

This table shows that after the construction of the micro dam in the lowlands, market gardeners practised 13 market garden cropping systems. This situation is the result of the colonisation of the lowlands, which has opened up more space for market gardening. This has led to the cultivation of mixed crops requiring extensive use of pesticides and fertilisers. Table 10 below shows that the use of pesticides and fertilisers by market gardeners increased after the development of the lowlands.

Table 10. Very high frequency of pesticide and fertiliser use after development.

Vegetables	Very important	Important	Somewhat important	Total	IFI%	Rank
Onion + tomato	240	52	3	295	90.21%	6
Tomatoe + cabblage	258	42	2	302	92.35%	5
Cabblage + tomato + onion	306	12	1	319	97.55%	2
African eggplant + onion + tomato	306	12	0	318	97.25%	3
Cucumber + cabblage	27	130	35	192	58.71%	7
Gumbo + African eggplant	27	100	50	177	54.13%	9
Gumbo + tomato + African eggplant	15	130	39	184	56.27%	8
Chilli + tomato + cabblage	315	2	3	320	97.86%	1
Gumbo + cucumber + onion	3	30	90	123	37.61%	11
Onion + mint + carrot	3	10	100	113	34.55%	12
Aeggplant + celery	0	2	108	110	33.64%	13
Onion + mint + cabblage	18	26	90	134	41%	10
Chill + onion + cabblage	270	30	4	304	92.96%	4

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

From this picture, we can see that there has been an increase in the use of pesticides and fertilisers. Cropping systems (onion+tomato, chill+onion+cabbage, chilli+tomato+cabblage, African eggplant +onion+tomato, cabbage+tomato+onion, tomato+cabblage) ont des IFI \geq 90%.

3. 3. Determinants of the heavy use of pesticides and fertilisers on market gardening sites after the development of the lowland

During the period 2011-2012, the lowland was effectively developed, resulting in the almost permanent presence of surface and groundwater in the Nedialpoun lowland. This

situation led to the colonisation of the lowland and the multiplication of market gardening systems. A decade later, i.e. 2014-2024, the number of market gardening systems continues to increase, accompanied by significant use of pesticides and fertilisers. Table 11 summarises the factors contributing to the use of pesticides and fertilisers.

Table 11. Factors affecting pesticide use on vegetable parcels.

		Estimate	Standard error	ddl	p-value	95% confidence interval	
						Lower bound	Upper bound
Limit	[Use of pesticides and fertilisers = 2]	15.353	1.643	1	0.00	12.133	18.572
	[Use of pesticides and fertilisers = 3]	19.013	1.639	1	0.00	15.8	22.226
Location	[sex = 1]	-0.161	0.852	1	0.85	-1.831	1.509
	[sex = 2]	0	.	0	.	.	.
	[age = 1]	0.542	2.429	1	0.823	-4.218	5.302
	[age = 2]	-0.104	2.474	1	0.967	-4.953	4.745
	[age = 3]	-0.677	2.299	1	0.768	-5.184	3.83
	[age = 4]	1.214	2.344	1	0.604	-3.38	5.809
	[age = 5]	-0.153	2.167	1	0.944	-4.4	4.094
	[age = 6]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
	[Number of households = 1]	1.064	1.769	1	0.547	-2.403	4.532
	[Number of households = 2]	0.93	1.725	1	0.59	-2.45	4.311
	[Number of households = 3]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
	[Level of education = 1]	-1.515	0.697	1	0.03	-2.881	-0.148
	[Level of education = 2]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
	[Income level = 1]	1.589	1.726	1	0.357	-1.793	4.971
	[Income level = 2]	2.59	1.915	1	0.176	-1.163	6.344
	[Income level = 3]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
	[Plot size = 1]	-1.292	0.674	1	0.055	-2.613	0.029
	[Plot size = 2]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
	[Plot size = 3]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
[Level of equipment = 1]	-20.961	2.537	1	0.00	-25.934	-15.987	

	[Level of equipment = 2]	0 ^a	.	0	.	.	.
	[Ground water level = 1]	-18.31	2.422	1	0.00	-23.057	-13.563
	[Ground water level = 2]	0.111	1.202	1	0.049	-2.246	2.467
	[climate = 1]	18.271	1.898	1	0.00	14.55	21.991
	[climate = 2]	17.906	2.387	1	0.00	13.228	22.584
	[Urban market = 1]	17.738	2.381	1	0.01	12.998	21.994
	[Local market = 2]	0	.	0	.	.	.
	[Type of vegetables used = 1]	-0.999	1.019	1	0.327	-2.996	0.998
	[Type of vegetables used = 2]	-2.263	0.845	1	0.07	-3.919	-0.606
Model Fit Information							
Model	Log likelihood - 2	Chi-square	ddl	p-value			
Constant only	182.881						
Final	70.747	112.134	23	0.000			
Fitting accuracy							
	Chi-square	ddl	p-value				
Pearson	459.943	141	00				
Deviance	138.100	141	0.553				
Speudo R ²							
Cox and Snell	0.63						
Nagalkerke	0.780						
McFadden	0.593						

Source: Field investigations, November - December, 2024

Table 11 shows that the type of vegetables grown, the type of market, climatic variables (temperature, rainfall), the level of the water table, the level of equipment, income and education influence the use of pesticides and fertilisers by market gardeners in the Nediapoun lowlands today. The type of vegetables grown and the type of market influence the use of pesticides and fertilisers (p-value < 5%), which could be explained by the fact that vegetables are oriented towards the urban centre (Koudougou is the third largest city in Burkina Faso).

This forces market gardeners to produce vegetables that use pesticides and fertilisers, such as tomatoes, onions, African eggplant and cabbage. It must be said that the dishes eaten in Koudougou often use vegetables grown by market gardeners. Gardeners therefore adapt their production to the needs of the people of Koudougou. Even if this strategy requires them to make

heavy use of pesticides and fertilisers. The size of the plot and the level of equipment are therefore significant (p -value $< 5\%$) and encourage the purchase of pesticides and fertilisers to increase the gardeners' profits.

In addition, Climatic factors also have a highly significant influence on pesticide use (p -value $< 0.05\%$). Extreme temperatures and high humidity (extreme rainfall) in the lowlands have increased (Yaméogo, 2024; Yaméogo & Rouamba, 2023), leading to a proliferation of species harmful to horticultural crops, according to 90% of respondents. This forces market gardeners to use more phytosanitary products. The availability of groundwater also influences the use of pesticides, as the drop in the water table in April, May and June forces market gardeners to produce quickly and massively during the period when the water table is high, i.e. between September, October, November, December, January and February.

4. DISCUSSION

4. 1. Cropping systems promoted in the lowlands of Burkina Faso and Africa

The study shows that market gardeners promote a diversity of market garden cropping systems. This diversity responds to market requirements and climatic conditions. This situation has been highlighted by several other authors who have worked on the lowlands of Burkina Faso. For example, Yanogo et al., 2019 found that market garden producers in the Villy Centre lowlands of west-central Burkina Faso practise a diversity of market garden cropping systems, dominated by onion + tomato + cabbage, and that the reasons for this are socio-economic in the Sourgou lowlands (Maiga, 2023, Yanogo & Maiga, 2023). Yameogo (2021) found the same results in a vegetable garden in the city of Koudougou, Burkina Faso. Other studies conducted in the Boucle du Mouhoun region also show that market gardeners grow a variety of vegetables on market garden plots in Lapara, in the commune of Boromo (Yaméogo et al., 2022), and West of Burkina Faso (Ouédraogo et al., 2019, Ouédraogo & Tapsoba, 2022).

4. 2. Factors influencing pesticide use in Burkina Faso and Africa

Pesticides and fertilisers are essential to market garden production in Burkina Faso and in the market garden site in the study area. The study showed that the type of vegetables used, the type of market targeted by the market gardeners, climatic variables, the level of the water table, the size of the plots, the level of equipment and the level of education led to the dynamics of pesticide and fertiliser use in the study area. These results are partially confirmed by Kara et al. (2024) for market gardens located in the two main cities of Burkina Faso (Ouagadougou and Bobo-Dioulasso). In fact, in the market garden sites, age, sex, accident rate, income level, use of credit, market gardening activity and the danger of pesticides are among the factors that lead to the adoption of pesticides. This difference could be explained by the fact that our study focuses on a peri-urban area, whereas the study carried out in Ouagadougou and Bobo-Dioulasso took place in an urban area.

This situation could change the way market gardeners perceive the situation. However, our results are similar to those of other studies carried out on market garden sites in Africa. In the Congo, on market garden sites, age, experience, income, production, gender, level of education and membership of an agricultural association had no significant influence on pesticide use (Atsamekou, 2023). In Ghana, in market gardening sites in the north and east of the country, pesticide use depends on farm size, farm income, mechanisation and contact with

extension services (Anang & Amikuzuno, 2015). In Ebonyi and Anambra states in south-eastern Nigeria, the economic incentive associated with yam production drives producers to increase pesticide use (Rahman & Chima, 2018).

5. CONCLUSION

Market gardening is an important activity in the study area of Burkina Faso. The study of the dynamics of market garden cropping systems and pesticide use was based on the perceptions of market gardeners. The study showed that market garden cropping systems and pesticide use increased significantly both before and after the development of the lowlands. Several factors were identified, including the type of crops grown, the type of market, the level of the water table and climatic variables. It would therefore be useful for the Réo commune authorities to take measures to reduce the use of pesticides and fertilisers, otherwise very serious environmental and health problems will arise in the area in the coming years.

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